

Magneto-Ionic Control of Coercivity and Domain-Wall Velocity in Co/Pd Multilayers by Electrochemical Hydrogen Loading

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Magneto-ionics, as the electrochemical reconfiguration of magnetic materials at low gating voltages, is a highly energy-efficient alternative to control magnetism. For the fastest magneto-ionic concept based on hydrogen, fundamental mechanisms are currently under debate, mainly because quantitative compositional information inside the magnetic materials upon gating is lacking. Using the electrochemical hydrogen loading of Co/Pd multilayers with perpendicular anisotropy, this study demonstrates that the hydrogen concentration inside the magnetic material determines its magnetic properties. Hydrogen concentrations up to a maximum of (0.24 ± 0.01) hydrogen atoms per metal atom can be set deterministically by voltage and are quantified via flow-cell coulometry. With increasing hydrogen concentration, a continuous increase in coercivity of up to 15% and a decrease in magnetic domain-wall velocity by an order of magnitude are observed using in situ MOKE microscopy. This enables the voltage-controlled stop-and-go of domain walls. These magneto-ionic effects can be explained by an increasing perpendicular anisotropy with increasing hydrogen content in Co/Pd multilayers, which is supported by theory. Importantly, the approach should be transferable to other ionic systems, such as lithium- or oxygen-based ones, where it can uncover the yet hidden effects of ionic concentration on the magnetic properties and guide the design of functional magneto-ionic devices.

consumption compared to conventional current- or field-controlled devices. A variety of technologies can be exploited to achieve VCM,^[5–7] with multiferroic,^[8] strain-based,^[9] charge-carrier doping,^[10] or magneto-ionic (i.e., electrochemical)^[11–14] approaches being prominent examples. The magneto-ionic approach is especially promising, as it could ultimately enable the non-volatile reconfiguration of magnets at low power by changing the magnet's internal composition electrochemically via the insertion of ions from an electrolyte. Using this mechanism, researchers have demonstrated the control of a variety of different magnetic phenomena, e.g. ferrimagnetism,^[15] diamagnetism,^[16] superparamagnetism,^[17] exchange-bias,^[18–21] Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya interaction (DMI),^[22] or Ruderman–Kittel–Kasuya–Yoshida (RKKY)-coupling.^[14,23] The magneto-ionic control of perpendicular magnetic anisotropy (PMA)^[24–28] has gained special attention in the scientific literature recently, as a result of the manifold possible applications, e.g. for magnetic data storage and spintronics.

While various types of ions can be used for magneto-ionics, hydrogen-ions, i.e., protons, have been in the research focus lately,^[17,23,28–33] due to their small size and fast diffusion ability. Hydrogen magneto-ionics are based on the electrochemical

1. Introduction

Voltage control of magnetism (VCM) is an important topic for magnetic devices,^[1–4] as it promises to reduce their power

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absorption of hydrogen into a magnetic host lattice. In general, electrochemical hydrogen absorption requires atomic hydrogen to be generated at the interface first, either via proton reduction or water splitting, with a subsequent diffusion step into the bulk of a magnetic material to follow.^[34] Absorbed hydrogen atoms in a material can then influence electronic, structural, and magnetic properties of the host. Surprisingly, in the magneto-ionic literature magnetic properties have never been studied as a function of absolute hydrogen concentration experimentally, as an accurate quantification of hydrogen in solids is challenging.

Hydrogen concentrations in solid electrodes can be assessed using a variety of techniques. Both thermogravimetric analysis with mass spectrometry^[31] and atom probe tomography^[32] have already been used to quantify hydrogen in magnetic electrodes after electrochemical hydrogen loading. However, such techniques require a high vacuum environment, which might lead to the unwanted outgassing of volatile hydrogen during sample transfer or evacuation. Indirect methods based on the detection of structural,^[35] magnetic,^[36] or resistive^[37] properties during hydrogen loading can be used alternatively, but they rely on accurate reference data for the calibration of hydrogen concentrations. For experimental methods that afford a depth profiling of hydrogen, e.g. nuclear reaction analysis^[38] or polarized neutron reflectometry,^[39] the extraction of hydrogen concentrations is also not straightforward. If a solid can be hydrogen-loaded electrochemically, coulometry is an alternative method, which yields average hydrogen concentrations with a low uncertainty, when conducted in an electrochemical flow cell.^[40] As an electrochemical technique, is also ideal for the study of magneto-ionic effects, which operate on the basis of electrochemical reactions per se. Here, we use flow cell coulometry for the quantification of hydrogen in our magneto-ionic device.

Most commonly, Co/Pd-based electrodes have been used for hydrogen magneto-ionics, as the hydrogen solubility is high for Pd (up to 0.7 H:Pd^[41]). Previous literature has discovered a marked influence of hydrogen on the magnetic properties of such Co/Pd-based materials, found in both gas-phase^[41–53] and electrochemical (magneto-ionic) loading experiments.^[17,28,30,33,54] For Co/Pd interfaces, the influence of hydrogen concentration on the magnetic properties has been addressed in a recent theoretical study. Klyukin et al.^[55] find a non-monotonous variation of PMA with hydrogen concentration: For a homogeneous distribution of hydrogen within the Co/Pd interface at low concentrations below ≈ 0.2 H per M atom, an increase in PMA is predicted, followed by a decrease of PMA at higher concentrations with an eventual in-plane transition for concentrations > 0.7 H per M atom.

For our experimental study, we selected Co/Pd multilayers as the electrode, as they enable the quantification of hydrogen via coulometry and allow testing the theoretical predication of PMA as a function of hydrogen concentration in an experiment. In order to rule out other magneto-electric effects, such as electrostatic charging, we also investigate isostructural Co/Pt multilayers that cannot absorb hydrogen, but exhibit the same layer structure and similar magnetic properties. The magnetic similarity of Pd- and Pt-based PMA multilayers is well-known, as they have been extensively studied in the context of magnetic recording.^[56–60]

In our study, we report a reversible increase of coercivity in the Co/Pd multilayer stacks upon application of a hydrogen-loading voltage through an aqueous electrolyte, which is not detected for

the Co/Pt system. We demonstrate that the hydrogen concentration in Co/Pd multilayers can be set and measured electrochemically and that coercivity is a function of that hydrogen concentration. We attribute changes in coercivity to a changing perpendicular anisotropy at the Co/Pd interfaces induced by hydrogen. We further show that the domain-wall velocity in the Co/Pd PMA system can be lowered by an order of magnitude upon hydrogen loading and demonstrate that domain-wall motion can be completely stopped upon hydrogen loading at a fixed field. While our study sheds light on the magneto-ionic mechanism for hydrogen in Co/Pd specifically, this first quantitative study of hydrogen concentration in a magnetic material can also have wide-ranging implications for the entire field of magneto-ionics and ionic functional materials, as our approach should be transferable to other ionic systems, e.g. based on lithium- or oxygen-ions.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Pd as a Key Material for Hydrogen Magneto-ionics

A key difference between Pd and Pt is the ability of Pd to absorb hydrogen in its crystal lattice. The solubility of hydrogen in Pd is ≈ 0.7 H/Pd at a H_2 pressure of 1atm and room temperature,^[61] while for Pt it is negligible ($\approx 10^{-11}$ H/Pt) under the same conditions.^[62] We exploit this difference in hydrogen solubility of the two metals in our first experiment.

The general structure of our multilayers is sketched in **Figure 1a**. Initially, we conduct cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments for $[Co/Pd]_3$ and $[Co/Pt]_3$ multilayers in sulfuric acid, which are shown in **Figure 1b**. We observe a strong cathodic current increase for both samples starting below -0.10 V, while after reversal of the scan direction a small anodic peak ≈ -0.15 V occurs only for $[Co/Pd]_3$, but not for $[Co/Pt]_3$. To understand this difference in the CV, we illustrate electrode reactions on Pd and Pt surfaces at cathodic potentials in **Figure 1c** top and bottom, respectively. When a Pd electrode is held at a cathodic potential in acidic solution, protons can be reduced at the surface forming adsorbed hydrogen atoms. These adsorbed hydrogen atoms can then undergo two different follow-up reactions, the absorption of hydrogen into the bulk of Pd and the recombination of two adsorbed hydrogen atoms on the surface to form a hydrogen molecule (H_2 gas evolution). Due to the negligible solubility of hydrogen in Pt, on a Pt- surface, as sketched at the bottom of **Figure 1c**, adsorbed hydrogen atoms can only recombine to form hydrogen molecules but cannot be absorbed. The same reactions are expected to occur on the surface of $[Co/Pd]_N$ and $[Co/Pt]_N$ multilayers, which are covered with either Pd or Pt. Consequently, the cathodic current increase for $[Co/Pd]_3$ in **Figure 1b** comprises currents from hydrogen absorption and H_2 gas evolution, while for $[Co/Pt]_3$ cathodic current can be attributed exclusively to gas evolution. The anodic current peak for $[Co/Pd]_3$, on the other hand, is the signature of the oxidation of previously adsorbed hydrogen atoms, which allows hydrogen quantification in the following.

To determine the influence of hydrogen on the magnetic properties of both Pd- and Pt-based multilayers, we employ them as working electrode in a two-electrode electrochemical cell suitable for in situ polar MOKE (magneto-optical Kerr effect) microscopy. For this experiment, we use fresh samples to rule out

Figure 1. Effect of voltage on [Co/Pd]₃, [Co/Pd]₅, and [Co/Pt]₃ multilayers in sulfuric acid. a) Scheme of the multilayers with three and five repeating [Co/Pd] units ($N = 3$, $N = 5$) and three repeating [Co/Pt] units which are tested for magneto-ionics. b) Cyclic voltammogram for [Co/Pd]₃ (black, solid line) and [Co/Pt]₃ (red, dashed line) in a flow cell setup at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} using three-electrode voltage U_{3E} on the x-axis. A hydrogen desorption peak around $U = -0.15 \text{ V}$ is only visible for [Co/Pd]₃, but not for [Co/Pt]₃. The schematic reactions on Pd- and Pt-based electrodes are shown in (c) top and bottom, respectively. Three-electrode voltages U_{3E} are only used in the voltammogram in (b) to facilitate comparability and are converted into two-electrode voltages U for hydrogen loading (-2.10 V) and unloading (-0.15 V) in the following, see also Figure S1 (Supporting Information). A small increase in coercivity at -2.10 V (red) is detected only for the Co/Pd multilayers with $N = 3$ and $N = 5$ in (e,h), respectively, as seen in the inset, but not for the isostructural Co/Pt multilayer with $N = 3$ in (f). The application of -0.15 V reverses this effect and leads to hysteresis loops comparable to the OCP loops.

any history effect originating from previous electrochemical measurements. In the as deposited state, the [Co/Pd]₃ and [Co/Pd]₅ multilayer (i) exhibit similar coercivities of $(80 \pm 2) \text{ mT}$ and $(83 \pm 2) \text{ mT}$, respectively, whereas the coercivity of the [Co/Pt]₃ multilayer is $(10.0 \pm 0.5) \text{ mT}$. The differences in coercivity between Pd and Pt-based multilayers reflect their differences in the PMA and thin film microstructure. After adding the sulfuric acid electrolyte, we wait for 30 min to reach stable conditions. We then measure hysteresis loops at the open circuit potential (OCP), upon application of a cathodic voltage for hydrogen loading (-2.10 V), and upon application of an anodic voltage (-0.15 V) for hydrogen unloading to test reversibility. Voltages

for loading and unloading are applied for 80 s in total. The hysteresis measurement for each step is started 15 s after the start of the voltage application. The voltages for hydrogen loading and unloading are deduced from Figure 1b, with the three-electrode voltages for the loading/unloading experiments ($U_{3E} = -0.10 \text{ V}$ corresponds to approximately $U_{2E} = -1.50 \text{ V}$). The cathodic voltage of -2.10 V used for hydrogen loading is well below the hydrogen reduction onset of -1.50 V (see two-electrode CV in the Figure S1, Supporting Information) to facilitate hydrogen absorption, while the hydrogen-unloading voltage is close to the open-circuit value.

Figure 2. Reversibility of the hydrogen-induced coercivity changes in $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ multilayers and structural stability after 100 cycles. a) Coercivity upon repeated hydrogen loading and unloading at constant voltages of -2.10 V and -0.15 V, respectively. Shaded regions represent the experimental error. AP denotes coercivity in the as-prepared state. b–d) X-ray diffraction spectra (b), X-ray reflectivity profile (c), and derived SLD depth profiles (d) in as-prepared state and after 100 cycles of hydrogen loading and unloading.

Figure 1d–f shows the resulting in situ polar MOKE hysteresis loops for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$, $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$ and $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_3$ multilayers, respectively. The hysteresis loops at OCP are similar to those of the as deposited state and coercivities amount to (79 ± 2) mT for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$, (83 ± 2) mT for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$, and (10.5 ± 0.5) mT for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_3$, respectively. Small differences to the as-prepared state may be related to minor chemical surface changes when adding the sulfuric acid, which may dissolve small amounts of surface oxide or Co, the latter in case of nanometer-sized scratches.

When hysteresis loops upon application of a hydrogen-loading voltage of -2.10 V (red curves) are compared to the OCP states, a coercivity increase of 6 and 4 mT is observed for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ and $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$ multilayers, respectively. In contrast, no observable changes are found for the $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_3$ sample. Switching the voltage back to a value of -0.15 V (green curve), reverses the changes in the hysteresis loop for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ and $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$, while the loop for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_3$ again remains unaltered.

We attribute the observed increase of coercivity in Co/Pd multilayers to hydrogen absorption into the multilayer stack. Absorbed hydrogen atoms can reach buried Co/Pd interfaces and grain boundaries via diffusion, where they can influence PMA or grain boundary pinning and thus coercivity. As mentioned in the introduction, a hydrogen-induced change in PMA has been predicted at Co/Pd interfaces by theory^[55] and is discussed in the context of our results in the next section. For Co/Pt multilayers only H_2 formation occurs, as hydrogen absorption is not possible

in Pt. The absence of a magneto-ionic effect for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_3$ therefore confirms that the observed magneto-ionic response for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_N$ can be traced back to hydrogen in the multilayer stack. Other magneto-electric effects such as oxygen-based reactions or electrostatic charging would be equally expected for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pt}]_N$ multilayers.

2.2. Reversibility of Hydrogen-Induced High Coercivity States in $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$

The reversibility of the magneto-ionic effect of the $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ sample from Figure 1d is further tested by continuing to switch the voltage between -2.10 and -0.15 V, for a total of 10 cycles. The coercivity values $\mu_0 H_C$ extracted from the hysteresis loops are displayed in Figure 2a. Coercivity values measured during the hydrogen-loading steps are shown as red points, those measured during unloading as green points.

Coercivity increases from the OCP state to the first and second hydrogen-loading step, which indicates that an equilibrium is reached only after a few cycles. This is likely due to an equilibration of hydrogen concentrations in the loaded and unloaded states, but might also be related to microstructural activation upon hydrogen loading, as previously suggested for a Pd-based heterostructure.^[19] From the third loading step on, both the higher coercivity in the hydrogen-loaded state and the lower coercivity in the hydrogen-unloaded state reach stable values and we

observe a reversible toggling between the two states for the next eight cycles.

The reversibility of the magneto-ionic effect and structural stability of the multilayers is then investigated for an even longer period of cycling. For this experiment, we prepared a [Co/Pd]₃ sample with a slightly thicker (6 nm total) Ta layer, which facilitates structural characterization by X-ray reflectivity (XRR) without changing the magnetic properties significantly. The reversible hydrogen-induced coercivity increase is systematically observed during the measured 100 cycles, (Figure S2, Supporting Information), with some variations due to the refill procedure. A comparison of X-ray diffraction (XRD) and XRR data measured in the as-prepared state and after the 100 cycles is shown in Figure 2b–d. In the XRD pattern, we observe a Bragg reflection closely above the Pd(111) lattice spacing value originating from the full 7.6 nm layer structure consisting of the [Co/Pd]₃ multilayer as well as the Pd cap and seed layer structure (the Ta is amorphous). There are also two Laue thickness oscillations visible at $2\theta = 39.25^\circ$ and $2\theta = 37.65^\circ$ to the left of the Bragg peak, indicating the overall smooth growth of our quasi Pd(111) textured layer structure and a low defect density in the multilayer.^[63] The XRR pattern in Figure 2c exhibits oscillations typical for multilayers, which are caused by interfering X-rays reflected from different layers. XRR profiles for the as-prepared state and the multilayer after 100 cycles are shifted on the intensity axis to enable comparison. The XRR curves are fitted with GenX 3^[64] to derive scattering length density (SLD) depth profiles, which confirm the nominal multilayer structure. The corresponding fits to our XRR data are shown in Figure S3 (Supporting Information). The XRD peak position, peak width, and Laue oscillations in (b), the XRR oscillations in (c), and the SLD profiles in (d) show no significant changes after 100 hydrogen-loading/-unloading cycles, confirming that the structure of the multilayer remains unchanged in the electrolyte and after extensive cycling.

In an additional experiment, we investigated the retention of the high coercivity state after loading, when switching to OCP (Figure S4, Supporting Information) instead of -0.15 V. The high-coercivity state proved to be non-volatile for a short timescale of ≈ 1 – 2 min, while for longer times the coercivity returns to the initial value.

2.3. The Critical Effect of Hydrogen Concentration on Coercivity

The thermodynamics of hydrogen concentration in palladium is well-understood from hydrogen-loading experiments using H₂ gas at different pressures.^[65–67] As the H₂-pressure and the electrochemical potential are linked via Nernst's equation,^[34] controlling the internal hydrogen concentration is also possible by selecting appropriate electrochemical potentials.^[68,69] In analogy, the equilibrium hydrogen concentration upon electrochemical hydrogen loading in Co/Pd multilayers should also be adjustable by the applied voltage, once it is below the threshold for hydrogen reduction. In the following, we show not only that hydrogen concentration can indeed be controlled in Co/Pd multilayers via voltage, but also demonstrate that coercivity is a function of this concentration.

In the first experiment shown in Figure 3a, we record hysteresis loops for a [Co/Pd]₃ multilayer upon the application of dif-

ferent loading voltages and subsequent constant unloading voltages. Voltages for loading and unloading are applied for 80 s in total, the hysteresis measurement for each step starts 15 s after voltage application. The corresponding coercivity values $\mu_0 H_C$ extracted from the hysteresis loops upon loading are shown as red points. Each of these hydrogen-loading steps is followed by an unloading step at a constant voltage ($U = -0.15$ V), with the corresponding coercivities shown as green points. At an onset voltage of -1.80 V coercivity starts to increase significantly with respect to the OCP state. The difference between hydrogen-loaded and -unloaded states is largest at a loading voltage of $U \approx -2.10$ V, which stays constant for even more negative loading voltages.

Next, we quantify average hydrogen concentrations x_H in our [Co/Pd]₃ multilayers, as the atomic ratio of hydrogen to metal (Pd and Co, including the Pd cap and seed layer), via coulometry in an electrochemical flow cell setup, which is shown in Figure S5 (Supporting Information). Hydrogen loading into the Ta seed layer is, while possible, not taken into account for our x_H values, as it occurs at much larger timescales compared to the Co/Pd top layers.^[70] The measured oxidation charge during the unloading step can be directly converted into x_H via Faraday's law provided that charge contributions from capacitive charging of the electrochemical double layer, hydrogen adsorption, and other electrochemical side reactions are excluded.^[40,71,72] The oxidation of hydrogen gas from within the electrolyte is an important side reaction, which can be avoided by the continuous exchange of the electrolyte solution in the flow cell setup during loading and unloading.^[40] The necessity of such a flow cell setup is underlined when comparing cyclic voltammetry measurements for [Co/Pd]₃ and [Co/Pt]₃ under static and flow conditions in Figures S6 and S7 (Supporting Information).

The x_H values as a function of loading voltage U shown in Figure 3c in red are obtained by repeating the same loading/unloading procedure (80 s steps, more negative loading voltages, constant unloading voltage) used to measure coercivity changes in Figure 3a in the electrochemical flow cell. The concentrations x_H are then calculated from the integral of oxidation current I with time t during unloading as

$$x_H = \frac{\int I(t) dt}{F (n_{Pd} + n_{Co})} \quad (1)$$

where F is Faraday's constant and n_i is the nominal amount of substance of Pd and Co, as defined by the total layer thickness and reference area exposed to the electrolyte. The measured oxidation current is corrected for the contribution of capacitive charging and hydrogen adsorption and a constant leakage current at the end of unloading (see Section S8, Supporting Information). The uncertainty in hydrogen concentration using this method is estimated to $\Delta x_H = \pm 0.01$ hydrogen atom per metal atom. The procedure for determining hydrogen concentration for a single unloading step is visualized in Figure S8 (Supporting Information).

Figure 3c shows a voltage-concentration isotherm for [Co/Pd]₃ multilayers and reveals that x_H values can be set deterministically by applying voltages below the hydrogen reduction threshold of $U = -1.50$ V. Such a voltage is reasonable in view of the minimum thermodynamic voltage difference of -1.23 V, which would be required for hydrogen reduction in our two-electrode

Figure 3. Hydrogen-loading voltage as the control parameter to set hydrogen concentration and coercivity in $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ multilayers. a) Coercivity $\mu_0 H_c$ during stepwise hydrogen loading and unloading. The voltage for hydrogen loading into one sample is set to successively more negative voltages (from -1.50 to -1.90 V in steps of 0.10 V and from -1.90 to -2.20 V in steps of 0.05 V), while the unloading voltage remains constant (-0.15 V). Shaded regions in (a) represent the experimental error. b) Relative changes of magnetic anisotropy energy (ΔMAE) in the out-of-plane direction as predicted by DFT for the shown Pd/Co/Pd trilayer in the region of low hydrogen concentrations, referenced to the zero-hydrogen state. Adapted from ref. [55]. Error bars are omitted for the sake of clarity. c) Coercivity in hydrogen-loaded state and hydrogen concentration x_{H} , as the atomic ratio of hydrogen to metal, plotted as a function of hydrogen-loading voltage U . Note the inverted x-axis. d) Relative changes in coercivity (ΔH_c) as a function of hydrogen concentration from our work, referenced to the OCP state.

cell with 1 M sulfuric acid, with water oxidation being the dominant reaction at the counter electrode. While such electrochemical setting of hydrogen concentration has been known for pure Pd,^[68,69] it is here demonstrated for the Co/Pd multilayer system for the first time. Our values of hydrogen concentration approach the equilibrium concentration at each voltage for the 80 s loading time in this experiment but have not quite reached full equilibrium within this timespan ($x_{\text{H}} = 0.29 \pm 0.01$ after 60 s at -2.10 V compared to $x_{\text{H}} = 0.33 \pm 0.01$ at saturation after 1200 s) as determined by hydrogen-charging tests as a function of loading time (Figure S9, Supporting Information). Nonetheless, the shape of our voltage-composition isotherm closely resembles the shape of equilibrium pressure-composition isotherms for PdCo alloys.^[73]

Equilibrium pressure-composition isotherms allow insights into the thermodynamics of hydrogen absorption. Two phases of hydrogen with palladium are known depending on the concentration: At low hydrogen concentrations the PdH_α solid solution phase forms exclusively, while at higher hydrogen concentrations the PdH_β hydride phase starts to grow at the expense of the PdH_α phase.^[67] Both phases share a rock salt crystal structure, with the main difference being the much larger lattice constant in the PdH_β phase. The coexistence region of both phases manifests itself in a steep increase of hydrogen concentration in the isotherm. While for pure Pd a sharp increase of concentration is

expected at a constant pressure,^[67] for CoPd alloys this increase of concentration occurs in a broader pressure range.^[73] The increase of hydrogen concentration in Figure 3c between voltages of $U = -1.70$ V and $U = -1.95$ V could therefore be indicative of the transition from PdH_α at more positive voltages to PdH_β at more negative voltages for $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ multilayers.

Maximum hydrogen concentrations in our Co/Pd multilayers are lower than literature values for bulk palladium ($\text{H/Pd} \approx 0.7$),^[61] which is reasonable in view of the cobalt interlayers, which have a low intrinsic hydrogen solubility ($\text{H/Co} < 10^{-4}$).^[74] A few reports investigating hydrogen loading into Co/Pd multilayers from the gas-phase, have also found a significantly reduced hydrogen solubility.^[52,70] Alloying of Co with Pd^[70,73] or stresses in the multilayers^[70,75] induced during deposition could be further reasons for the low maximum hydrogen concentration and influence the shape of the voltage-concentration isotherm in our multilayer samples. In hydrogen-charging experiments for $[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$ in Figure S10 (Supporting Information) we find qualitatively a similar shape of the isotherm compared to $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$, but even smaller hydrogen concentrations overall for the multilayer with a larger number of Co interlayers. One conceivable explanation for this finding lies in the aspect of intermixing of Co and Pd layers during sputter deposition. Considering the multilayers including Pd cap and seed layers as fully

intermixed, hypothetical alloys, one would obtain a Co concentration of $\approx 25\%$ for the $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$ multilayer and $\approx 20\%$ for the $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ multilayer from the nominal layer structures. Although the scenario of a full intermixing of Co and Pd is unlikely in our case, relative Co concentrations could be higher for $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$ at partially intermixed interfaces, leading to the smaller hydrogen concentrations. A limited penetration of hydrogen through Co layers is another explanation, which could explain the decreased hydrogen concentration in $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_5$ compared to $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$.

Besides hydrogen concentration x_{H} , coercivity $\mu_0 H_{\text{C}}$ is also plotted as a function of hydrogen-loading voltage U in Figure 3c in black. Both x_{H} and H_{C} are clearly correlated, which is reflected in the simultaneous first significant increase of both coercivity and hydrogen concentration at the onset voltage of $U = -1.80$ V and a simultaneous levelling off at voltages more negative than $U = -1.95$ V. From these data we infer that the deterministic setting of different hydrogen concentrations by voltage can be used to control coercivity in Co/Pd multilayers.

Theoretical calculations provide an explanation for the concentration dependence of coercivity: An increasing PMA with increasing hydrogen concentration is predicted up to < 0.2 H per M atom in a Pd/Co/Pd trilayer,^[55] when homogenous hydrogen loading of both Pd and Co, which is accompanied by lattice expansion, is assumed (inset in Figure 3b). Both, an increase of PMA and a reversible lattice expansion have previously been evidenced for gas phase hydrogenated Pd/Co/Pd trilayers with Co layer thicknesses of 0.3–0.4 nm.^[50]

These relative changes in the out-of-plane magnetic anisotropy energy (MAE) from ref. [55] are plotted in Figure 3b as a function of hydrogen concentration. For our $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ multilayer, the effective MAE as calculated from the out-of-plane and in-plane $M(H)$ curves, measured by SQUID vibrating sample magnetometry, amounts to 160 ± 30 kJ m^{-3} (Figure S11, Supporting Information). The hydrogen-induced MAE changes cannot be directly determined by measuring the in-plane (hard axis) $M(H)$ curves by in situ longitudinal MOKE microscopy, because the experimental magnetic field range (116 mT) is small compared to the magnetic anisotropy field $\mu_0 H_{\text{A}}$ of > 2 T and superimposed optical effects cannot be disentangled (not shown). However, Figure 3d shows that the monotonous increase in out-of-plane coercivity observed in our experiments increases with hydrogen concentration in a similar manner as the relative MAE changes in Figure 3b from the theoretical calculations. This comparison is an indication that the observed coercivity changes can be explained by a hydrogen-induced increase in out-of-plane MAE.

Besides this expected reversible change in MAE, which is accompanied by reversible structural changes, hydrogen-induced changes in microstructure may also influence coercivity. Irreversible hydrogen-induced microstructural changes, such the formation of voids, cracks, or delamination can be ruled out as a cause for the observed reversible changes.^[34] However, hydrogen insertion may also lead to the formation of reversible defects, which disappear again upon hydrogen unloading. For example, segregation of hydrogen in grain boundaries, hydrogen-induced surface lattice disorder and the formation of hydrogen-traps in the alpha-phase can occur and can be reversible in thin films and nanoparticles.^[34,71] Such microstructural changes may lead to changes of the domain-wall nucleation and pinning potential landscape, and thus affect coercivity.^[31,76,77] As such de-

fects are often filled with hydrogen preferentially, an impact on coercivity is expected in the regime of low overall hydrogen concentrations (see discussion in Section 2.4). In our case, however, the magneto-ionic effect becomes prominent at concentrations $x_{\text{H}} > 0.05$ (compare Figure 3d). Furthermore, hydrogen-loading tests on a multilayer with in-plane anisotropy in Figure S12 (Supporting Information) do not show a similar hydrogen-induced increase in coercivity. Both aspects are indications that a hydrogen-induced change in microstructure affecting domain-wall pinning is not dominant in our case.

At higher hydrogen concentrations a decrease of PMA is also predicted in the theoretical study, which we cannot confirm experimentally due to the limited maximum hydrogen solubility in our multilayer systems. We juxtapose our experimental findings and the theoretical prediction of PMA over the full range of concentrations in Figure S13 (Supporting Information). It should be noted that our experimental method for measuring hydrogen-to-metal ratios x_{H} yields a mean hydrogen concentration averaged over the full stack, thus the H per metal atom value could differ locally at the Co/Pd interfaces.

2.4. Voltage-Controlled Stop-and-Go of Domains by Hydrogen-Tunable Domain-Wall Velocity

We further investigate the influence of hydrogen loading on the domain-wall velocity for Co/Pd multilayers, as not only coercivity and magnetization reversal in PMA multilayers are governed by domain-wall motion, but the controllable domain-wall motion by itself is of importance for domain-wall logic^[78] and memory devices.^[79]

Domain-wall velocities in PMA materials strongly depend on the magnitude of the applied magnetic field and are very sensitive to defects causing domain wall pinning. At low magnetic fields the domain wall has to overcome the local propagation energy barriers by thermal activation.^[77] Magnetization reversal then proceeds via the thermally-activated, stepwise reversal of discrete volumes (Barkhausen volumes) at the domain boundaries. This gives rise to the typical jagged structure of the domain walls in PMA materials,^[80] as seen in the domain images in Figure 4c. On a macroscopic scale one can identify a mean domain-wall velocity, by taking the average over a sufficiently large number of such reversal steps. The applied magnetic field (the driving field) determines the number of reversal steps in a given time frame and thus defines an average domain-wall velocity.

We capture the domain-wall dynamics in our multilayers in real time using our MOKE microscopy setup and extract domain-wall velocities from magnetization relaxation experiments, where the normalized magnetization M/M_{s} is recorded as a function of time t at a constant out-of-plane field after previous saturation in the opposite direction. In Figure 4a magnetization relaxation curves are shown for the same $[\text{Co}/\text{Pd}]_3$ sample in the unloaded/dry (green) and hydrogen-loaded state (red) for a field of 68 mT. The fraction of relaxed magnetization M/M_{s} is obtained from the reversed area in corresponding MOKE videos (black to grey ratio). Qualitatively all relaxation curves have a similar profile, indicating a common reversal mechanism via domain-wall propagation, which we also observe in the MOKE images shown at selected times in the insets. In line with our expectation,

Figure 4. Hydrogen-controlled magnetization reversal and domain-wall velocity. a) Magnetization reversal as a function of time recorded via MOKE microscopy in a hydrogen-unloaded, dry state (green) and hydrogen-loaded state (red) at 68 mT for [Co/Pd]₃. Corresponding domain images (557 μm × 348 μm) for both states are shown for the highlighted times. The inset shows the applied magnetic field as a dashed line in comparison to the coercivity of hydrogen-unloaded and -loaded hysteresis curves. b) Averaged domain-wall velocity as a function of magnetic field in a hydrogen-unloaded, dry state (green) and hydrogen-loaded state (red) for [Co/Pd]₃. Dashed lines are linear fits to the data. Note the logarithmic scaling on the axes for time *t* and domain wall velocity *v*. c,d) Show the equivalent experiments as (a,b), respectively, but for [Co/Pd]₅ multilayers. Hydrogen loading increases the magnetic field required to obtain similar domain-wall velocities by ≈6 mT for [Co/Pd]₃ and by ≈4 mT for [Co/Pd]₅.

magnetization reversal progresses more slowly in the hydrogen-loaded state compared to the unloaded state.

The average domain-wall velocity in the hydrogen-loaded and -unloaded [Co/Pd]₃ is displayed for the same sample in a wider range of magnetic fields in Figure 4b. For both loaded and unloaded states the domain-wall velocity increases exponentially with the applied magnetic field. At a given magnetic field, the domain-wall velocity is about an order of magnitude lower in the hydrogen-loaded state compared to the unloaded state. The analogous experiments for [Co/Pd]₅ multilayers are depicted in Figure 4c,d. Our overall findings for [Co/Pd]₅ are similar to [Co/Pd]₃, with generally larger driving fields for domain-wall motion for [Co/Pd]₅. Domain-wall velocity, however, decreases again by about one order of magnitude in the hydrogen-loaded state for [Co/Pd]₅. A strong reduction of domain-wall velocity has been shown before via hydrogen loading of a CoPd alloy from the gas phase^[77] and is demonstrated for the electrochemical hydrogen loading of Co/Pd multilayers in the present work. The possible origin of the decreasing domain-wall velocity upon hydrogen loading is discussed in the following.

The exponential increase of domain-wall velocity *v* with the applied field *H* evident from Figure 4b,d supports previous findings in Co/Pd multilayers that domain-wall motion is a thermally activated process in the used field range.^[81] Thermally activated domain-wall motion is expected in both the creep regime and the depinning regime, which can only be discerned by measuring the domain-wall velocity over many orders of magnitude.^[82,83] In

both cases, the mean domain-wall velocity *v* can be expressed via an Arrhenius equation:^[80]

$$v = v_0 \exp \left[-\frac{E_p - 2M_s V_B H}{k_B T} \right] \quad (2)$$

where *v*₀ is a constant prefactor, *E*_p the activation energy for domain-wall propagation, *M*_s the saturation magnetization, *V*_B is the Barkhausen volume, i.e., the volume in which magnetization is reversed in a single switching event, *H* the applied magnetic field, and *k*_B*T* the thermal energy. In an alternative yet equivalent representation, the activation energy for domain-wall propagation *E*_p can be replaced using a propagation field *H*_p = *E*_p/2*M*_s*V*_B:^[80]

$$v = v_0 \exp \left[\frac{2M_s V_B}{k_B T} (H - H_p) \right] \quad (3)$$

The propagation field *H*_p equals the coercivity *H*_c expected at *T* → 0 K.^[80] According to Equation (3), the domain-wall velocity should vary linearly with the magnetic field in a logarithmic representation:

$$\ln(v) = \ln(v_0) + \frac{2M_s V_B}{k_B T} (H - H_p) \quad (4)$$

In a logarithmic plot of domain-wall velocity as a function of magnetic field, the propagation field thus defines a shift on the field axis. Increasing the intrinsic propagation field H_p of a material, would thus lead to a linear velocity curve shifted to the right, i.e., to larger magnetic fields H along the x-axis. We observe such a lateral shift in velocity in Figure 4b,d for the hydrogen-loaded multilayers compared to the unloaded ones for both $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ and $[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$ multilayers. In contrast, the slopes are not significantly changed upon hydrogen loading. Comparing quantitatively, the shift in H_c obtained from hysteresis loops is 6 mT for $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ from Figure 1d and 4 mT for $[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$ from Figure 1e, which matches the lateral curve shifts in Figure 4 within the measurement uncertainty.

The decreased domain-wall velocity and increased coercive and propagation field in hydrogen-loaded multilayers are in agreement with each other and seem to share the same origin. Based on the theoretical prediction,^[55] we hypothesize that in all cases the dominant contribution is an increase of PMA, as discussed above for Figure 3c, but changes in saturation magnetization and the reversible, hydrogen-induced trapping of domain walls may also play a role. The discussion of the semilogarithmic plots in Figure 4b,d can help disentangle these factors to some extent. On the one hand, since H_p is proportional to the square root of the effective magnetic anisotropy,^[84] the theoretically predicted increase of MAE (see Figure 3b) upon hydrogen loading would readily explain a shift in H_p . On the other hand, the Barkhausen volume V_B is very sensitive to a change of the defect structure. V_B can be expressed as $V_B = L_B^2 t$, where t is the multilayer thickness and L_B is the Barkhausen activation length. L_B is related to the mean distance between strong domain-wall pinning centers.^[85,86] Thus, an increasing number of defects, which act as domain wall pinning sites, typically results in a decrease of L_B .^[83,87] From the slopes in Figure 4b,d, which correspond to $\frac{2M_s V_B}{k_B T}$, very similar activation lengths of 21 (18) nm for the unloaded and 19 (18) nm for the hydrogen-loaded state are estimated for the $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ ($[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$) multilayers, respectively (Section S14, Supporting Information). This is only a rough estimation, as changes in M_s , which are not considered in the calculation, cannot be fully excluded and may mask defect-induced changes in V_B . The invariance of L_B indicates that no new pinning sites for domain walls are introduced in our multilayers upon hydrogen loading. The similar appearance of domain-wall boundaries (jaggedness) in MOKE images before and after hydrogen loading (Figure 4a,c) supports this notion that no new pinning sites are created.

The invariance of L_B does not rule out that existing domain wall pinning sites in the original multilayer structure, such as grain boundaries, are modified upon hydrogen loading. Previous works on other material systems indicate that hydrogen loading in grain boundaries can play an important role for hydrogen-induced coercivity changes.^[32,77] Therefore, a stronger pinning of domain walls at the grain boundaries upon hydrogen loading may be another possible mechanism for the coercivity increase observed in our multilayers. Grain boundaries in Pd act as traps for hydrogen atoms, that are typically filled with hydrogen preferentially at low overall hydrogen concentrations, prior to the $\text{PdH}_\alpha / \text{PdH}_\beta$ - phase transition.^[88,89] Hence, possible changes of domain-wall pinning due to hydrogen loading of grain

boundaries should be prominent at low overall hydrogen concentration (well below $x_H < 0.05$, the onset of the phase transition in our case). We observe no significant changes in coercivity at such low hydrogen concentrations in our $[\text{Co/Pd}]_3$ multilayers in Figure 3c,d. Larger changes in coercivity only occur at hydrogen concentrations $x_H > 0.05$. Based on these considerations we suggest that a hydrogen-tuning of grain boundary properties could only play a minor role in our multilayers, and that the major coercivity changes observed at larger x_H are primarily related to an increase of MAE.

Lastly, we seek to exploit the controllable domain-wall velocity for a stop-and-go functionality of domain-wall motion. An experiment to achieve that functionality is presented in Figure 5 for a $[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$ multilayer. Prior to the first voltage pulse we applied an unloading voltage of -0.15 V for > 5 min initializing a hydrogen-free state. We select a magnetic field of 63 mT for magnetization reversal for a $[\text{Co/Pd}]_5$ multilayer, well below the experimentally measured coercivity of 83 mT as seen in the inset, which gives rise to a low domain-wall velocity in the hydrogen-unloaded state. At this constant field, we allow magnetization to relax in a part of the observed multilayer area and then evaluate M/M_s upon application of a voltage profile to the multilayer stack, which is shown in Figure 5b. Corresponding MOKE images showing the position of the domain wall are depicted for every 5 s during the experiment in Figure 5a with the right edges of the MOKE images matching the corresponding times on the x-axis. The applied voltage profile consists of three 10 s voltage pulses for hydrogen loading at -2.10 V, interrupting the otherwise constant voltage for hydrogen unloading at -0.15 V.

Apart from the changes due to domain wall motion, the MOKE images in Figure 5a, show changes in the image contrast in the uniformly magnetized areas in the hydrogen-loaded states as compared to the unloaded states. The Kerr intensity, which is responsible for the image contrast, is influenced by the orientation and magnitude of magnetic moment, but also the optical properties. A decrease of saturation magnetization has previously been found for Co/Pd multilayers loaded with hydrogen from the gas phase^[47,48] and is also predicted by theory.^[55] However, a decrease in MOKE intensity for continuous Co/Pd multilayer films upon hydrogenation has also been attributed to reflectance changes.^[51] A decrease in reflectance upon hydrogen loading from the gas phase has also been reported for thin Pd films.^[90] Based on additional experiments evaluating MOKE intensity provided in Figure S15 (Supporting Information), we hypothesize that intensity changes in Figure 5a are related to a change of optical properties, rather than to changes of saturation magnetization in our case. In order to solely assess the effect of hydrogen on the domain-wall motion in Figure 5, the M/M_s curves shown in Figure 5b are corrected for these optical effects.

Two seconds after the application of a hydrogen-loading pulse (shown for the third pulse from $t = 82$ s to 90 s in the inset), magnetization relaxation stagnates, and M/M_s reaches a plateau. The corresponding MOKE images in Figure 5a in the hydrogen-loaded state at $t = 85$ s, show a domain wall at an almost unchanged position compared to the prior image, taken at $t = 80$ s before hydrogen loading, and at exactly the same position compared to the following image, taken at $t = 90$ s later during the

Figure 5. Voltage-controlled stop-and-go domain-wall motion in a [Co/Pd]₅ multilayer. a) MOKE images tracking the position of a domain wall are shown as vertical stripes for every 5 s of the experiment (starting from 5 s on the left to 110 s on the right). b) Hydrogen-loading voltage pulses at -2.10 V are applied to the multilayer, while simultaneously recording the magnetization relaxation curves as M/M_S at a constant field of 63 mT. The left inset shows the applied magnetic field as a dashed line in comparison to the coercivity of hydrogen-unloaded and -loaded hysteresis curves. Domain-wall motion stops after ≈ 2 s of hydrogen loading, as evidenced by the plateaus in M/M_S (also shown in the inset in the middle) and the almost unchanged position of the domain-wall during the pulse in (a). Domain walls gradually resume their movement after switching back to hydrogen unloading (-0.15 V) (shown in the right inset) and reach a constant velocity after ≈ 10 s. Note the inverted voltage axis in (b). A full movie of this experiment is available in the (Section S16, Supporting Information).

same hydrogen-loading pulse, confirming that domain-wall motion has stopped in the hydrogen-loaded state. At the following unloading step starting at $t = 90$ s (second inset), magnetization relaxation gradually resumes, and it takes ≈ 10 s until the domain walls reach a constant velocity comparable to that of their initial motion. The previous two hydrogen-loading pulses (starting at $t = 20$ and 50 s, respectively) have the same effect of stopping the movement of the domain-wall and causing a plateau in the magnetization relaxation curve. Domain-walls continue their movement during the hydrogen-unloading phases.

In view of energy efficiency, the use of OCP state instead of an unloading voltage of -0.15 V would be beneficial. In this case, however, the restart of the domain-wall motion is delayed significantly compared to the unloading at -0.15 V (Section S17, Supporting Information). The time-delay in the response of the domain-wall velocity is related to the finite kinetics of hydrogen absorption and desorption. A faster response can be envisioned in the future by engineering the electrode/electrolyte interface and multilayer structure to increase kinetics of charge transfer and hydrogen diffusion.

At this point we attempt to compare our approach to the voltage control of domain-wall motion with other existing concepts. Strain-based devices have proven an effective way to achieve controllable domain wall motion,^[91,92] however, they require comparably large voltages for operation in the order of $\Delta U = 10$ to 100 V. Using electric fields via the application of gate voltages through solid^[93–97] or liquid^[98] gate dielectrics has also been demonstrated, where typically voltage differences between $\Delta U =$

5 and 15 V are needed for a change in domain-wall velocity of an order of magnitude. Reports on the electrochemical/magneto-ionic control of domain-walls are scarce,^[22,99,100] but generally operate at lower voltages ≈ 1 V. In order to compare all these experiments with large differences in the applied field and velocity ranges (ranging from 10 to 1000 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ as in this work, up to the 100 m s^{-1} range^[22,97,98]), we contrast the voltages needed for an order of magnitude change in domain-wall velocity. Using this metric, our magneto-ionic mechanism based on hydrogen ($\Delta U = -2.10$ V) compares favorably to devices based on strain and electric field and performs similarly with respect to other magneto-ionic concepts. The applied voltage may be further decreased in the future by optimization of the electrode/electrolyte interface at the working and counter electrode to enhance kinetics and thus reduce overvoltage. We envisage that our mechanism can also be used in other Pd-based materials^[101,102] for the control of domain-wall velocity at low voltages. While such a magneto-ionic control of domain-wall velocity offers perspectives for energy-efficient domain-wall-logic devices,^[78] the complete stop-and-go functionality for domain-wall movement might find additional applicability, e.g. in a voltage-controlled magnetic shift register.^[98]

3. Conclusion

We have shown that coercivity in Co/Pd multilayers can be reversibly increased via magneto-ionic hydrogen loading using low voltages. A magneto-ionic response in isostructural Co/Pt has not

been observed in our experiments, which we relate to the limited hydrogen solubility of Pt compared to Pd. We find that coercivity is sensitive to the overall hydrogen concentration in Co/Pd multilayers, a connection that is experimentally established in magneto-ionics for the first time. The measurement of concentration yields a metric that can be compared to theoretical predictions from simulations and thus enhances the understanding of microscopic mechanisms in magneto-ionics.

Our results are in line with an increasing PMA at the Co/Pd interfaces at low hydrogen concentrations found in a recent theoretical investigation of the Co/Pd system,^[55] although a hydrogen-induced trapping of domain-walls at grain boundaries might also play a minor role. Hydrogen concentration in our work can be set deterministically using the thermodynamic relation of concentration with voltage and approach equilibrium concentrations for the duration of our loading experiments. Maximum hydrogen concentrations of ≈ 0.25 H:M are attained, which are smaller than the bulk value for Pd of 0.7 H:Pd, likely due to the intermixing of Pd with Co at the interfaces or stresses in the multilayer. Microstructural engineering might allow increasing the maximum hydrogen concentration in our multilayers in the future and test the theoretical prediction in the regime of large hydrogen concentrations.

Furthermore, our used coulometric technique is not only sensitive to hydrogen, but can measure concentrations for any ionic species in an ionic target in general, provided there is only a single, reversible electrochemical reaction. In cathode materials for Li-ion batteries, for example, a coulometric quantification of Li⁺ concentration is standard during battery charging and discharging and should be easily transferable to magneto-ionic electrodes. For battery cathodes, it has already been shown that magnetic susceptibility^[103,104] depends on the Li⁺ concentration, a correlation of great importance for magneto-ionic materials based on Li⁺. In analogy, we expect similar correlations between concentration and magnetic properties for alternative oxygen- or nitrogen-based magneto-ionic devices.

Finally, we have demonstrated that domain-wall velocity in Co/Pd multilayers in the thermally-activated regime is reduced by an order of magnitude upon hydrogen loading, which is shown to be related to the increasing coercivity. The control of domain wall velocity can be exploited to bring domain-wall motion to a complete halt upon hydrogen loading. In terms of applied voltage for a one order of magnitude change in domain-wall velocity our approach compares favorably to existing concepts. We envisage that the reported hydrogen-based magneto-ionic control of domain-walls can be further improved in terms of field range and velocity, so that it could offer a lower-power electric handle on future domain-wall logic and data storage devices.

4. Experimental Section

Sample Preparation: Multilayer stacks in this study were fabricated using dc magnetron sputtering in a 4×10^{-3} mbar Ar atmosphere in an ultrahigh vacuum ATC 2200 system from AJA International Inc. Si wafers with 2 nm thick native oxidized (SiO₂) layer were used as substrates. Prior to the multilayer deposition, a 1.5 nm Ta layer was deposited for adhesion purposes. A subsequent M(3 nm) layer (M = Pd, Pt) serves as a seed in order to obtain a preferred Co/M (0001)/(111)-texture, which supports larger PMA. M denotes the respective transition

metal Pt or Pd in the multilayer stack. The samples were finally capped by a 2 nm M layer to avoid surface oxidation. All metallic layers were deposited at room temperature utilizing alternating source shutters. To ensure uniform growth of the entire stack, the sample holder was set in rotation at ≈ 120 rpm. The final multilayer stacks had the general structure Ta(1.5 nm)M(3 nm)[Co(0.4 nm)M(0.7 nm)]_NM(1.3 nm), where N is the number of Co/Pt or Co/Pd bilayer repeats (N = 3 and N = 5). Wafers were cut into (1 × 1) cm² pieces for further processing.

X-Ray Diffraction and X-Ray Reflectivity: The XRR and XRD measurements were performed using a Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer with a 9 kW rotating anode and Cu K_α radiation. For XRR, the samples were measured in parallel beam geometry with a Cu K_β-filter and a step size of 0.004°. XRD measurements were performed in parallel beam geometry using a two-bounce Ge(220) monochromator (Cu K_{α1}), with a step size of 0.05°. The measured XRR profiles were fitted using the software GenX version 3.6.22^[64] using the spec_inhom model.

In Situ MOKE Microscopy: An electrochemical cell designed for the use with a MOKE microscope^[18] using an electromagnet in out-of-plane geometry was employed for in situ measurements. This electrochemical cell was directly embedded in a custom-made sample holder for MOKE microscopy, which provides wire feedthroughs for contacting the electrodes to a potentiostat. An O-ring was used to define the sample area (38.5 mm²) in contact with the electrolyte and to seal the bottom of the cell. The electrolyte compartment contained 200 μL of 1 M sulfuric acid and was positioned directly above the pole shoe of the electromagnet. A Hall probe was used to calibrate the magnetic field at the sample position in the cell. The electrochemical cell was connected to either a Biologic-SP50 or a Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat, which were used to control electrochemical experiments in combination with magnetic measurements. All voltages are referenced to a Pt-wire, which was used as counter electrode in a 2-electrode configuration. This wire was inserted into the electrolyte compartment and positioned at a distance of ≈ 3 mm to the sample surface. A Zeiss LD Plan-Neofluar objective lens with a 20x magnification was focused on the sample surface through the electrolyte for the measurement of magnetization curves and domain images. The subtraction of a background image before magnetization reversal was used to enhance contrast in the domain images. For MOKE magnetometry, hysteresis loops were mathematically corrected for contributions from a linear intensity drift and a parasitic intensity increase stemming from the magneto-optical Faraday effect (see Figure S18, Supporting Information).^[105] This effect occurs when perpendicular magnetic fields are acting on the objective lens, which rotates the plane of polarization of incident light proportional to the applied magnetic field.

Flow-Cell Electrochemistry: Cyclic voltammetry and hydrogen-loading/-unloading experiments for the determination of hydrogen concentration were conducted in a custom-made electrolyte flow cell in a Teflon compartment, which is depicted in Figure S5 (Supporting Information). The samples were mounted horizontally as the working electrode at the bottom of the compartment and an O-ring defined a circular surface area of 50.3 mm² of the multilayers in contact with the electrolyte. The flow cell was connected to an electrolyte reservoir. The electrolyte was 1 M sulfuric acid (conductivity 453 mS/cm at 22 °C). Dissolved oxygen and hydrogen were removed from the electrolyte via continuous N₂-bubbling in the reservoir. The electrolyte was pumped at a fixed flow rate of 30 mL s⁻¹ through an opening of the otherwise sealed flow cell directly onto the sample surface for a complete electrolyte exchange and removal of hydrogen bubbles. Flow cell experiments were controlled using an Metrohm Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat. A Pt wire was used as the counter electrode in a two-electrode configuration to mimic the experimental conditions in the in situ MOKE cell. Hydrogen concentrations x_H were calculated from the charge during oxidation steps (hydrogen-unloading), which is converted into moles via Faraday's law according to Equation (2). The amount of Pd and Co were determined from the thickness of individual layers as defined by the sputtered structure and the area exposed to the electrolyte solution using the densities of bulk Co (8.90 g cm⁻³) and Pd (11.99 g cm⁻³).

Measurements of Domain-Wall Velocity: For the determination of domain-wall velocity at a constant magnetic field the samples were first

saturated in the negative field direction, before switching to the desired field in the positive direction. A background image was subtracted to enhance contrast for different magnetization directions before initiating magnetization relaxation by applying a small field of opposite polarity. Videos at a frame rate of 27 fps were recorded monitoring magnetization reversal. In post-processing, videos were binarized using Otsu's method,^[106] when the differently magnetized areas were accessible as white and black pixel counts respectively. In order to account for the non-linear propagation of domains in the image frame, the domain-wall velocity was calculated from the total area of the measured segment and the relaxation time, which is the time for a complete reversal of magnetization. Due to fluctuations of MOKE intensity caused by the electrolyte, magnetization reversal was considered to start when the pixel count reached 99.9 % of the maximum and completed when 0.1 % of the original pixel count was reached, effectively averaging the domain-wall velocity over the entire reversal curve. The domain-wall velocity obtained using this method was in good agreement with velocities obtained from the manual extraction of distances and times traveled by a linear domain segment from a video and a subsequent linear fit.

For the experiments on hydrogen-induced stop-and-go of domain wall motion, the integrated intensity curve was corrected for hydrogen-induced Kerr intensity variations not related to magnetization reversal, i.e., purely optical effects such as change in reflectance. This correction was carried out by evaluating the intensity changes within part of the image of Figure 5a (upper light grey area) which does not include the domain wall. This intensity background was then subtracted from the integrated intensity curve of the full image to achieve the curve corresponding to M/M_s curve related to magnetization reversal by domain wall movement only, without hydrogen-induced optical effects.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11549805>, reference number 11549805.

Keywords

hydrogen-loading, magnetic multilayers, magneto-ionics, perpendicular anisotropy

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